

FDI Policies of Vietnam Since 1977

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Abstract

FDI plays an important role in promoting the economic development of a country. In the globalization, the FDI wave has grown rapidly and become an essential source of capital for developing countries. In Vietnam, FDI contributes 20.13% of GDP, accounts for 72% of total export value, about 50% of industrial output (Central Economic Committee). Vietnam is the third-largest destination for foreign direct investment (FDI) in Southeast Asia, driven by its strategic location, competitive labor costs, and rapidly growing consumer market. The FDI policies in Vietnam has undergone many modifications and upgrade to be suitable with the new context of the international condition. FDI has contributed a large proportion to the completion of socio-economic development plan targets and is one of the most important external resources of Vietnam in the process of industrialization and modernization of the country.

Keywords: FDI, Policies, Vietnam.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 International Condition in the 1980s

In the Cold War, the international economy appeared with many extremely complicated developments. A fundamental feature of the commerce of this period was ideological cooperation. The Soviet Union established Council for Mutual Economic Cooperation (Comecon) with Eastern European countries with many disadvantages because of the cumbersome and awkward institutional arrangements for trade within the Soviet Union. By the 1970s and 1980s, the world had a series of economic crises: the oil shock of the 1970s caused by the Arab oil embargo; the second oil shock in 1979 caused by the revolution in Iran; The stock market crashed in the US, Asia and Europe in 1987. These crises caused major countries such as Canada, Australia, Japan, or the US to be caught in a downward spiral.

At the same time, in Eastern Europe and the Soviet Union, the rigidity of the centrally planned economy also revealed many weaknesses. The economic growth rate in the period 1965-1970 was 7.7% per year, in the period 1980-1985 it decreased to 3.6% per year (Mark Harrison, 2000). The Soviet government tried to reform, most notably the economic reform effort of Prime Minister Aleksei Nikolayevich Kosygin or the reform of General Secretary Gorbachov, leading to the collapse of the Soviet Union. After the World War II, the US become stronger than ever with huge amount of gold reserve and a numbers of talents scholars from all around the world. The development of technology, transportation and communication made it easy to move goods and manage processes remotely, thereby facilitating the development of FDI. Europe and Japan need the USA to rebuild the country's economy after the war. In that context, the United States adopted a foreign investment policy in particular and a tax system in general that favored foreign investments. In the late 1970s, many countries in Asia and Africa achieved their independence and started the process of building and developing their countries with inward policies. Some countries tightened their restrictive policies on FDI. In this period, the FDI wave mainly flows from the U.S to the West and its alliance.

However, the world economy was in stagnation in the 1980s. Industrial countries faced economic recession, the debt crisis happened in Latin America and East Asia, and developing countries grew slowly and lagged behind the world economy due to their inward policy. This situation has forced many countries to adjust their policy structures to reorient their economies. These adjustments include reducing tariffs, liberalizing the business environment, and deregulation of FDI. As a result, FDI inflows into developing countries began to increase in the second half of the 1980s.

1.2 Vietnamese background before 1986

In 1975, when Vietnam was completely independent and unified, starting to build consolidation and socialism with many challenges and difficulties after many long wars. Besides, the US also extended the embargo against Vietnam in all fields from 1975. Decades of arms embargo by the US and Western countries have exhausted Vietnam in all aspects. After the war, Vietnam made many efforts to restore its severely damaged economy, gradually establishing new production relations. The economy at that time had two main economic types, state-owned enterprises, and collectives, only a few individual economic types, no private and foreign-invested economy. In the 1980s, Vietnam was in a state of serious economic crisis, the operation of the centralized, bureaucratic and subsidized mechanism caused the Vietnamese economy to stagnate, the inflation rate reached over 700% in 1986. The average growth rate in the years 1981 - 1985 was 6.4% and 1986 - 1990 was 3.9% (MPI, 2018). Many state-owned enterprises and small-scale handicraft cooperatives produced in moderation, even closed or dissolved, causing very bad effects on the socio-economic situation. In general, economic growth during this period was low and inefficient. Vietnam has faced with the difficult situation of the country in the post-war period, which urgently needed new resources to support development investment and the Government soon realized the importance of foreign investment. It is urgent to have a legal framework for foreign investment to have a basis for implementation in practice to welcome capital flows. The above socio-economic situation has required Vietnam to find new solutions to boost the economic development.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research utilizes mixed-methods research methodologies to study the improvement of Vietnam's FDI policies since 1977 and their relationship with foreign direct investment inflows and economic outcomes.

Data collection: The study uses relevant secondary data obtained from reputable national and international sources, including the General Statistics Office of Vietnam, the Ministry of Planning and Investment, UNCTAD, and World Bank. These datasets include indicators such as annual FDI inflows, the number and sectoral distribution of FDI projects, GDP growth, and comparative FDI data from regional peers. The study also draws on information including FDI laws and amendments, government white papers, academic literature, and where possible, semi-structured interviews with experts, policymakers, and investors involved in Vietnam's investment policy landscape.

Data analysis is used to summarize FDI trends over time, identify key policy reform milestones and their correlation with changes in investment patterns, and assess the impact of major reforms (e.g., the 1987 FDI Law, WTO accession in 2007) on investment inflows using time-series and regression analysis techniques. It is used to examine the political, legal, and institutional context behind policy changes, understand the motivations and limitations of reforms, and evaluate their practical effectiveness through thematic and historical analysis.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Period 1977 - 1986

In 1977, Vietnam introduced its first legal framework for foreign direct investment through the Investment Charter (Decree No. 115/CP), marking the country's initial step toward economic openness. Initiated by Deputy Prime Minister Dang Viet Chau, the Charter emphasized respect for national sovereignty and mutual benefit, regardless of the investor's political system. While it provided a legal basis for FDI, it lacked detailed procedures and relied on the Ministry of Foreign Trade for licensing and oversight. Although existing for 10 years from its promulgation in 1977 to the Law on Foreign Investment in Vietnam in 1987, the 1977 Investment Charter has not been effective in practice. Vietnam has not granted any investment license according to the order and procedures specified in the Investment Charter in 1977. Three main reasons can be mentioned as following.

Firstly, in that period, the official intergovernmental aid still occupies an extremely important place in the relations of the socialist countries during that period. The leadership team at that time still had a sense of anti-capitalist imperialism because they had just come out of the war, so there were still a lot of controversies and disagreements. As a result, the implementation of this law faces many difficulties.

Secondly, after 1975, the political situation of the southwestern border and the northern border of Vietnam was not stable, making international investors feel insecure to invest in Vietnam. The investment license period is too short, from 10 to 15 years from the date of issuance of the investment license (Article 9); The corporate tax rate is too high: 30%, 40%, 50% (Article 15); For the joint-venture, the foreign capital contribution may not exceed 49% (Article 7). These are also obstacles for the investors to overcome.

Thirdly, in the context 2 years after reunion, this is the first document relating to FDI sector and the communist Government has no experience in this area. There were no synchronous policies with the Investment Charter of 1977 to attract investment. In this period, international investment and integration are still unfamiliar issues and have not yet received attention and focus.

However, the 1977 Investment Charter has partly demonstrated effort of the Government to put foreign capital in a legal framework to recover the economic development. This charter has covered all aspects of the business process, creating the initial legal framework for foreign investment activities and basis for the next steps. After the reform in 1986, the Foreign Investment Law in 1987 was upgraded and improved base on the 1977 Investment Charter.

3.2 Period 1987-1990

In December 1986, Vietnam's 6th National Party Congress initiated key policies aimed at reviving the economy, marking a significant shift toward social and economic reform. The country pursued a dual strategy of internal economic restructuring and international integration, overcoming blockades and embargoes, leading to notable economic growth. A major breakthrough was the expansion of international exchanges to attract foreign investment. Recognizing the inefficiency of state-owned and collective economies, leaders prioritized foreign capital to stimulate domestic growth. This vision materialized in the Foreign Investment Law of 1987, which outlined policies to encourage foreign direct investment (FDI). In 1989, the State Committee for Cooperation and Investment (SCCI) was established to manage foreign investment activities. The law, consisting of 6 chapters and 42 articles, was clear and transparent, making it more attractive than regional counterparts and surpassing the previous 1977 Decree.

It is a legal foundation for business cooperation. The Foreign Investment Law of 1987 has more specific provisions on the subject of investment cooperation for both Vietnamese and foreign parties or the field of investment promotion and foreign investment management agencies or includes the guarantee of investment capital and the interests of foreign organizations and individuals. In addition, there are provisions allowing foreign investors to repatriate capital and profits. This has created a solid rationale when investing in Vietnam. The minimum capital contribution ratio of foreign investors is 30%, and no maximum limitation.

It gives incentives to investors with of financial and credit supports. Many various investment incentives are granted. Vietnam offers tax holidays for two years which can be followed by another two years of half of the regular tax rate. In priority sectors, the corporate income tax is lowered from 10-25% for FDI. In order to encourage reinvestment of profits, enterprises are refunded the profit taxes for reinvested funds. Likewise, companies with foreign capital do not have to pay import duties on raw materials and other inputs or components used for the manufacturing of exports. The same is true for machinery and equipment imports. License requirements for FDI projects were eased which is a considerable advantage because of the long delays often caused by the rather restrictive policy on imports.

It changes awareness and viewpoint towards foreign economic sector. In the Law on Foreign Investment in Vietnam in 1987, the form of investment with 100% foreign capital had been first recognized as a Vietnamese legal entity, established in the form of a limited liability company. This change has reduced the protection of domestic enterprises, is a step forward in attracting and using FDI capital under the motto of multilateralization and diversification of foreign relations. Because for that time, countries with more open economies such as Thailand, Indonesia and other countries in the region do not yet have 100% foreign-owned enterprises.

In the first three years from 1988 to 1990, FDI did not have a clear impact on the socio-economic situation of Vietnam. From 1988-1990, Vietnam attracted only 213 projects with a registered capital of USD 1602.2 million and a legal capital of USD 1279.7 million, while the realized capital is insignificant because FDI enterprises after being licensed have to do many necessary procedures to bring capital into Vietnam (MPI, 2018). There were many reasons for this disappointing result. Vietnam's GDP per capita at that time was only 100-200 USD, a fledgling economy had just passed the threshold in 1986. Material deprivation, technological backwardness, economic difficulties are barriers for investors. The US trade and investment embargo were lasted until 1994 and state agencies from the central to local levels have not yet had the necessary experience in FDI activities. The condition that only enterprises belonging to the state-owned economic sector are allowed to cooperate with foreign partners in the joint-venture is also a limitation. Large corporations are not always interested in joint ventures with state-owned enterprises and they decided to withdraw from Vietnam. In general, the promulgation of the Law and the basic content of the Law is in line with the general regional trend, with the goal of encouraging foreign organizations and individuals to invest capital and technology in Vietnam.

3.3 Period 1990-1996

From 1991, Vietnam lost a huge amount of aid from the Soviet Union and the socialist countries of Eastern Europe. Thus, in the face of embargo and a significant shortage of foreign investment, to improve market access and national trade capacity Vietnam has strengthened its international integration by participating in discussions on bilateral, regional and multilateral agreements such as: restoring relations with international financial institutions, signing a trade agreement with the EU (1992) or joining the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) in 1995, normalizing Vietnam-US relations, applying to join the WTO (1995).

After 2.5 years of limited success, the Foreign Investment Law of 1987 was amended twice in 1990 and 1992. During this time, the Law on Private Enterprises and the Law on Companies were introduced in 1990, recognizing private ownership of production means and the right to establish private companies, marking a significant shift towards a multi-sector economy. These changes aimed to attract more capital as global investment fluctuated, reflecting evolving socio-economic and financial goals. In September 1993, the government issued Decree 39/ND-CP, which clarified the functions and duties of the State Committee for Cooperation and Investment. This period focused on promoting investment, strengthening management of project implementation, and overseeing the production process of licensed enterprises. Additionally, a new Department of Foreign Investment Project Management was established to support these efforts.

Reducing the protectionism of domestic enterprises and providing more incentives for foreign investors. Firms with 100% of foreign capital can enjoy tax incentives like a joint venture such as exempting profits for up to 2 years, reducing 50% of profit tax for a period of 2 years, which is limited in the law of 1987. The 1992 amendment granted foreign investors with more rights and incentives, allowing FDI in construction of infrastructure facilities, and providing foreign firms with longer operation duration. Specifically, for the form of business cooperation contract, there are new articles allowing private enterprises (previously allowing only limited liability companies and joint-stock companies) to become independent entities. Since 1992, all Vietnamese enterprises of all economic sectors are allowed to independently and directly cooperate with foreign firms. This amendment has encouraged foreign firms to set up 100% owned affiliates when entering the Vietnamese market.

Expand investment forms, improve investment quality. The 1992 law allows new forms of investment including BOT (Build-Operate-Transfer), BTO (Build-Transfer-Operate) and BT (Build-Transfer) contracts, specifically in the fields of transport, electricity, investment in mountainous and remote areas. These are very practical contents to facilitate socio-economic development for disadvantaged areas after a long period of receiving foreign capital. In this period, the government focused on attracting foreign investment in export-oriented fields (from 80% products or more) and high technology. Preferential policies have also begun to pay attention to investment quality, shifting to projects that effectively use natural resources, education, high-quality services, R&D and export-oriented projects.

Simplifying administrative procedures, strengthening state management. The amended policy decentralized of coordination in the state management of foreign investment on the basis of a one-stop mechanism, which taking the state management agency in charge of investment as the focal point. The administrative decentralization has fostered the development of both local businesses and foreign investment, thereby improving management efficiency and the principle of democratic centralism. It strongly encouraged foreign investment with easier regulations on the duration of investment licenses and other types of permits. It also simplified procedures and reduced time for granting investment license from 90 days to 60 days.

After 10 years from 1987 to 1997 with many changes in Investment policies, the FDI attraction in Vietnam was quite impressive. After each policy adjustment, the amount of registered FDI increased at different rates. From 1991 to 1996, the first wave of FDI took place with 2,230 projects and registered capital of 16,244 billion USD, realized capital of 13 billion USD (Tran Thi Anh Dao and Dang Thi Thanh Binh, 2013).

Chart 1: Licensed capital and number of projects of FDI in Vietnam, 1988-1996

Source: Ministry of Planning and Investment

Besides the above achievement, the Law on Foreign Investment 1987, amended and supplemented in 1990, 1992 still has limitations. The operating time of FDI enterprises in Vietnam is still limited to under 50 years, in special cases not more than 70 years, while Thailand and the Philippines do not have the limitation. Investment procedures are still cumbersome, discouraging FDI capital into Vietnam and reduced competitiveness compared to other countries in the region. These limitations have indirectly prevented Vietnam from taking advantage of many partners in terms of capital and technology, especially for large-scale and long-term projects.

3.4 Period 1996-2000

In 1996, the Law on Foreign Investment 1987 was amended and supplemented for the 3rd time. Vietnam has issued many tax incentives for FDI enterprises. The Government gave detailed guiding for the implementation of the Law on Foreign Investment, which stipulating the expansion of the level of tax incentives, the scope of tax incentives and the duration of tax exemption and reduction for FDI enterprises.

According to the provisions of the Law on Corporate Income Tax in 1997, FDI enterprises are entitled to the common tax rate of 25% (Article 10, Decree No. 30/1998/ND-CP), the tax rate applicable to domestic enterprises is at 32% (Article 10.2, Law on CIT 1997). Tax incentives such as tax exemption for 2 years, reduction of 50% of tax payable in the next 2 years and possibly up to 4 years if many investment encouragement standards are met, will continue to be applied to FDI enterprises. For special cases, the tax exemption period is up to 8 years.

This period was characterized by the sharp fall in FDI inflows to Vietnam, as a result of the Asian financial crisis. Newly licensed capital decreased on average at 24 percent per annum, while implemented capital went down more slowly, at 14 percent per annum on average, changing the ratios of registered and implemented capital. Since 1999, implemented capital has always exceeded registered capital.

In 1997 the committed capital was 4.6 billion dollars, in 1998 was dollars 3.8 billion dollars (-17%), in 1999 1.5 billion dollars only (-60%). Some 800 licensed projects have been withdrawn or revoked during this period, mostly from the crisis-hit Asian economies (Le Dang Doanh, 2002). After the Asian financial and monetary crises, countries in the region have considerably improved their investment environment to attract FDI.

Similarly, since that landmark, Vietnam has also changed its FDI policies dramatically. However, there still exist numerous claims from foreign investors about the lack of transparency, consistency, and effectiveness of legal enforcement in Vietnam’s law and regulations, despite the positive changes. These factors increase transaction cost for investors and make Vietnam’s investment environment become less attractive than previously, and less attractive than some countries in the region, especially China.

Table 1: Top 5 FDI Countries and Territories in Vietnam 1988-2000

Rank	Countries and territories	Number of projects	Capital (\$ mill)	% of total cumulative FDI
1	Singapore	254	5,775.8	14.9
2	Taiwan	703	5,190.2	13.4
3	Japan	338	3,576.0	9.2
4	Hong Kong	329	3,363.9	8.7
5	South Korea	312	3,159.3	8.1

Source: UNCTAD

3.5 Period 2000-2005

Although Vietnam has amended the FDI policy several times, the outcomes did not meet expectations. As a result, the Vietnam government decided to have additional amendments to the FDI policy as preparation for a strong globalization trend. Besides continuing to inherit those rules that had been successful in attracting FDI inflows into Vietnam, the Law on Foreign Investment changed in 2000 added two new articles of law and had 21 amended and supplemented compared to the 1996 version. The updated version of 2000 aimed to help remove all difficulties and obstacles of foreign businesses when they invest in Vietnam and increase the attractiveness and competitiveness of Vietnam's environment of investment.

The 2000 amendment to Vietnam's FDI policy aimed to reduce investment barriers and business risks for foreign enterprises. Key changes included allowing foreign firms to open accounts at foreign banks (with approval), facilitating faster international transactions, and permitting them to mortgage land-use rights to secure loans from licensed credit institutions. These reforms were designed to improve capital access and lower financial risks for international investors.

There were many changes in the policy aiming to pull more foreign capital inflow in Vietnam. But the most highlighted one was the tax policy. The Government replaced the Law on Profit Tax and the tax on profit transfer to foreign countries was abolished. The Law on Corporate Income Tax allowed the application of several incentives to promote investment, such as tax exemption in the first two years for newly established manufacturing facilities and a 50% tax reduction over the next 2 years; if investing in areas, industries, and economic zones enjoying tax incentives, they could enjoy lower tax rates than other projects. The longest period of exemption and reduction was 13 years (4 years of exemption, 9 years of reduction).

Chart 2: FDI OF VIETNAM FROM 2000 TO 2005

Source: Statistical Yearbook 2000, 2005, General Statistics Office of Vietnam

The amended FDI policy introduced tax incentives for activities like production expansion, technological innovation, and environmental improvements. Exporters benefited from 0% VAT, tax refunds, and corporate tax reductions, especially for high-export-value businesses. These measures aimed to lower export costs, enhance competitiveness, and make Vietnam's investment environment more attractive in the context of global economic integration.

In this period, FDI inflows into Vietnam started to recover after the previous stage but the pace was still slow. There was a slight increase in the number of FDI projects in this period but a relative stability in both the capital account and the total investment. The reason for this may be because the investment procedures of Vietnam at that time were still complex and the environment of investment was not so attractive compared to others despite Vietnamese efforts to complete the policy. In terms of economic structure foreign investors have focused on industries (oil and gas, manufacturing and processing industries like garments and footwear, food products, beverages) accounting for 2.743 projects with total committed capital of 23 billion US\$, corresponding to 60.0% of projects and 55% of committed capital. Agriculture, fishing and forestry share only 11% of the total projects (428 projects) and 3.6% of committed capital. The tertiary sector (hotels, restaurants, transportation and communication and other service industries) accounting for 21.6% of the total projects and 40% of the total committed capital (Le Dang Doanh, 2002).

At the end of 2005, FDI enterprises have attracted about 70,000 additional employees, bringing the total number of direct employees in the FDI sector 86.5 thousand employees, an increase of 17.8% over the same period of 2004. Newly registered investment capital increased by 81.8% and realized capital increased by 14.5% over the same period of 2004. There were 95 multinational companies with over 230 FDI projects in Vietnam with a total registered capital (including capital increase) of 10.6 billion USD, accounting for 20% of the total registered capital. Most of the companies mentioned above invest in large-scale projects (average over 45 million USD/project). At the same time, there is an increasing trend of small and medium-sized FDI enterprises in Vietnam. The average registered capital per project has decreased from 12 million USD/project in the period 1996-2000 to 3 million USD/project in 2001-2005. The FDI sector accounted for about 25% of total investment, 34% of

manufacture and 23% of export but provided only 0.3% of overall employment in Vietnam. FDI from more than 50 countries and economies around the world with the top 5 were Singapore, Taiwan, Japan, South Korea and Hongkong (MPI, 2018).

3.6. Period 2005-2014

In 2005, the National Assembly promulgated the Law on Investment and took effect from July 1st, 2006. The Law on Investment 2005 replaced the Law on Foreign Investment and the Law on Promotion of Domestic Investment. After that, the Government issued Decree 108/2006/ND-CP in September, 2006 detailing and guiding a number of articles of the Investment Law (Decree 108). This is the first time after nearly 20 years of implementing the Doi Moi policy that Vietnam has a legal framework on investment and enterprises that is uniformly applied to all investors and businesses of all economic sectors. The contents related to the organizational structure and operation of the enterprise were transferred to the adjusted Law on Enterprises. Other specific regulations such as tax were mentioned in the relevant specialized laws.

The 2005 Investment Law standardized key investment principles and notably decentralized the approval process for investment certificates. Local authorities were empowered to approve qualifying projects without central government involvement, simplifying procedures for investors. The law also promoted equal treatment of domestic and foreign firms and expanded the role of provincial and municipal governments in managing and promoting FDI. Those FDI projects with a capital scale of less than 300 billion VND, which are not on the List of Conditional Investment Areas, are delegated to the provinces and cities (Vo, T T and Nguyen, A D, 2012).

Compared to the previous periods, numbers of all indicators related to FDI have been greatly increasing. Especially, in 2008, just after one-year Vietnam participated in WTO, the number of total capitals registered reached its peak despite the world economy struggling with the global economy crisis. The number of new projects rose from 811 in 2004 to 987 in 2006, and to over 1500 in 2007 and 2008. Total registered capital went up even more quickly, from over 4.5 billion USD in 2004 to above 12 billion USD in 2006, before peaking at 71.7 billion USD in 2008. Similarly, implemented capital increased more rapidly than in previous years, to US\$4.1 billion in 2006, and 11.5 billion USD in 2008, as compared to about 2.8 billion USD in 2004. More importantly, unlike previous years, FDI attraction in 2008 was characterized by presence of many large projects, each of which has billions of USD in registered capital (Vo, T T and Nguyen, A D, 2012).

Due to the negative impact of the global financial crisis and Vietnam's domestic economic downturn since late 2008, the pace of new FDI registration and the implementation of several FDI projects, particularly large ones, slowed significantly. The number of projects fell dramatically to approximately 1,200 in 2009 and 1,186 in 2011. Total registered capital went down even more sharply, reaching only over USD 23.1 billion in 2009 and USD 15.6 billion in 2011. Implemented capital decreased more slowly, to USD 10 billion in 2009 and around USD 11.0 billion in 2010-2011. Thus, the share of FDI as part of total investment in Vietnam went down to only 25.7 percent in 2009, despite a minor recovery to 25.9 percent in 2011 (Vo, T T and Nguyen, A D, 2012). This shows the positive bright spot in the environment of investment in Vietnam. Since then, each year, the investment law has been adjusted and supplemented to suit the needs and changes of the world. Although it is not much, it can be seen how greatly Vietnam has made efforts in international integration in general and international economic integration in particular.

The cumulative registered FDI in Vietnam from 1988 to the end of 2014, reached about 290 billion USD, in which realized FDI is about 124 billion USD (accounting for about 43% and average annual realized FDI is about 4.8 billion USD). In the period 2005-2014, realized FDI capital was only about 42% of the total with registered capital. Vietnam attracted about 12 thousand projects, the

average investment capital is about 7.48 million USD/project, which is low value and difficult to attract high-technology. In the period 2005-2014, FDI enterprises accounted about 22.7% of the total investment, contributed about 15.1%-16.4% of Vietnam's GDP and about 38% to economic growth. FDI in Vietnam mainly focuses on the industrial sector while Vietnam has great advantages in seaport services, optical equipment, agriculture, forestry and seafood. On average, it contributed 13.9% to the total state budget though the ratio decreased from about 33.3% in 2006 to about 14% in 2014. Comparing with the share of 16.4% in GDP, this number is not quite commensurate. FDI played a great role in total exports of Vietnam with the share increased from 57.2% in 2005 to 62.5% by 2014. In 2014, FDI enterprises created about 3.45 million jobs, accounting for 6.4% of the total labor force and made up about 1/6 of the national GDP (VIR, 2020).

3.7. Period 2014-2024

The Investment Law (amended) was passed on November 26th, 2014 and took effect from July 2015. This Law includes 7 chapters, 76 articles, regulations on business investment activities in Vietnam; investment conditions and procedures; rights and obligations of investors; preferential policies and investment guarantees; State management over investment activities. The 2014 amended Investment Law is reflected in the following specific innovations.

Firstly, citizens are free to invest and do business in industries and professions that are not prohibited by the Law. The List of industries and trades banned from business investment and the List of industries and trades with conditional business investment in the Law according to the method of exclusion (selected) have contributed to the fundamental renewal of the application principle. Accordingly, investors are free to invest in all industries and trades not prohibited or regulated by this law.

Secondly, update regulations on the State's guarantee of property ownership of investors and commitment to adequate and fair compensation in case of appropriate expropriation or nationalization of investors' assets; Completing regulations on the State's guarantee of non-discriminatory treatment among investors in accordance with Vietnam's commitments under international treaties; Completing regulations on the application of the non-retroactive principle in case the legal document changes which adversely affects the investment incentives already applied to investors.

Thirdly, completing regulations on industries and professions that are eligible for investment incentives in order to improve the quality and efficiency of investment attraction. The revised Law has perfected the provisions of the current Investment Law on investment incentive industries and professions as well as principles and conditions for preferential application to ensure the attraction of FDI on industries using high technology and modern techniques, investment on large-scale production, labor-intensive rural areas, supporting industry and socialization sectors (healthcare, education, vocational training, culture, etc.

The government continued to reform administrative procedures by simplifying the process for granting investment registration certificates, reducing the time for foreign investors from 45 days to 15 days. In alignment with economic transformation strategies, the tax policy was also reformed, gradually lowering the corporate income tax rate: from 28% (2001-2008) to 25% (2009-2013), 22% (2014-2015), and 20% starting in 2016. The highest preferential tax rate was set at 10% for 15 years, with tax exemptions for 4 years and a 50% reduction in taxes for the following 9 years for new investment projects in sectors like IT, software, renewable energy, and environmental protection. Additionally, the government introduced the Authorized Economic Operator (AEO) Certification, offering FDI enterprises benefits in customs procedures, tax incentives, and preferential policies for import-export activities, provided they meet legal requirements.

Chart 3: FDI of Vietnam, 2006-2020

Data source: GSO 2018, Statista.com

In 2020, Vietnam was hailed as "a bright star in the COVID-19 dark sky" by the World Bank, thanks to a 2.9% GDP growth rate despite the global pandemic. By June 2021, foreign investment disbursements reached US\$9.24 billion, a 6.8% increase from 2020, with a strong FDI of US\$10.13 billion in the first quarter of 2021, marking an 18.5% year-on-year growth. FDI now contributes about 20% of Vietnam's GDP and 23.7% of total investment capital. It is mainly concentrated in processing and manufacturing, generating over 50% of the country's industrial production and a large portion of exports. The sector also provides nearly 4 million direct jobs and 5 million indirect jobs. FDI is a key driver of Vietnam's economic growth and plays a crucial role in developing the high-quality service industry. The average income in the FDI sector is about 11.2 million VND/month, 1.2 times higher than the national average (VIR, 2020).

In 2020, through the adoption of the amended Investment Law and Enterprises Law, the Vietnamese Government has taken many positive actions such as establishing specialized groups to the wave of investment when the world has been repositioning the supply chain and production after the Covid-19 pandemic, and creating a favorable business environment for enterprises. Besides, Vietnam's signing of the RCEP, UKVFTA; Major FTAs such as EVFTA, CPTPP is creating great opportunities for Vietnam to integrate and participate more deeply in the production network and select quality FDI projects to move up the ladder in the global value chain.

Compared with the 2014 Investment Law, the Investment Law 2020 has 22 new points, of which some following things are important and notable:

- 1) It introduces the definition of "Creative Start-up Project" for the first time, which has created a new topic for organizations associated with startup investment projects. On the basis of exploiting intellectual property, technology, new models, launching projects that can be quickly applied. For start-ups, foreign investors will not need to carry out investment registration procedures. For investment funds about the creation of technology, there is no need to register for investment, but only need to continue to register the business. This thing has mean for create

an environment setting up a light up. In addition, priority facilities are expanded to include all newly created centers, and research and development centers are also included in priority investment.

- 2) Stipulating principles, conditions, business investment in one document. In the past, the principles and conditions of investment and business are stipulated in many different documents, causing widespread and unsystematic phenomena, thereby trapping investors. Firms will only need to apply in one form: license or certificate without having to confirm in written certification from a state agency.
- 3) Investment law 2020 has added more preferential and the "fast depreciation" regulation, helping businesses and investors reach breakeven faster. In addition, the cost rates already discounted when calculating taxes have been increased. The legislator also gives priority to businesses that employ women and ethnic minorities.
- 4) Expanding investment priority objects such as: social house construction, subsidies products prioritized for development; technology-incubation, environmental protection; large-scale projects from 6000 billion VND with conditions on revenue or number of employees.
- 5) M&A projects with share of FDI firms more than 50% have to submit for acceptance. Besides, M&A activities relating to national security and defense, locating in areas with important positions must obtain approval from authorities.
- 6) The transferred land with a land use right by a FDI firm, which has been transferred the land use right from another party when proposing the first project on that same land, there will be no need to continue bidding to select an investor. Besides that, there are some adjustments relating to change of the owner of the investment program; change the land use process; change in total capital investment; change the project implementation schedule; Active time of the capital project; The changing technology has been validated. Thereby, we realize that the reduction of procedures is the main program, the goal towards the legislator

4. DISCUSSION

In addition to great opportunities, Vietnam also faces many difficulties and challenges in the process of attracting FDI, especially in the context of unpredictable developments in the world economy due to the aftermath of the pandemic. consequences of the trade war and the Covid-19 pandemic. Vietnam has achieved a phenomenal success in absorbing large levels of FDI, which have helped it cushion occasional spells of foreign exchange droughts over the last decade. However, Vietnam's FDI policy framework and incentive system may need further reform to improve the quality and quantum of FDI, especially in the face of the fierce competition among ASEAN economies. In particular, Vietnam can draw some lessons in attracting foreign investment by using of proper policies to support FDI.

Tax policy

Taxes are used as a key means to attract FDI and direct FDI flows into key industries and regions. The average tax rate for foreign-invested companies in Vietnam is between 10 and 25% compared to the capital gains tax rate for domestic companies of 32%. With this tax rate, Vietnam is relatively attractive compared to other countries in the region. However, our tax exemption period is from 2 to 4 years, while Singapore and Malaysia's income tax exemption period are from 3 to 8 years. Tax-free for a period of up to 15 years, or business type only subject to the income tax rate of 4%/year. In the Philippines, the average period of tax exemption is from 4 to 6 years, and income tax exemption for foreigners is implemented for 3 years from the time the business is profitable. In the Philippines,

special economic zones enjoy a lot of tax incentives such as VAT exemption, excise tax, profit transfer tax between branches, that Vietnam does not have. In general, Vietnam's tax policy still has many problems that we have not been able to implement, thus reducing its attractiveness compared to other countries in the region.

Legal issues

The autonomy of enterprises with 100% foreign capital according to international commitments has become a barrier to inspection and examination by Vietnamese authorities, leading to the lack of transparency among investors in tax declaration and payment activities. In addition, the form of mergers and acquisitions (M&A) is being interested by foreign investors in the process of our country divesting capital and shares of state-owned enterprises, which leads to the risk foreigners "take control" of important economic sectors and regions, strategic locations that directly affect national defense and security if not closely appraised.

Some projects also consume energy, natural resources and pollute the environment. The level of connection, attraction and technology transfer of the foreign investment sector to the domestic investment sector is still low. The foreign investment sector is mainly processing and assembling, the localization rate in some industries is low, the added value per unit of product is not high, Vietnam is still dependent on foreign technology and energy. The endogenous force of technology has not been created and promoted.

Meanwhile, some localities still allow foreigners to stand behind Vietnamese investors to invest in key areas and strategic locations, negatively affecting the security and the safety of the area. Because of the immediate and subjective interests in attracting foreign direct investment capital, some sectors and localities lack appraisal and capacity assessment of foreign investors, and are still permissive in policies on land lease and taxes payment and technology requirements. In particular, a number of strategic locations and areas with national defense and security value have been leased and used by foreign enterprises for a period beyond the provisions of the law. In particular, some countries have used disguised investors as "tools" to influence and influence the defense and security of other countries in the process of investment, production and business. This is an issue that greatly affects the defense and security of the country, the construction of a local defense area and the performance of military and defense tasks when situations arise.

Infrastructure facilities

Infrastructure is one of the factors that make it attractive to FDI. The fact also shows that it is difficult for countries with weak infrastructure to attract foreign investors. Over the years, Vietnam's technical infrastructure has improved step by step, partly meeting the requirements of socio-economic development in general and affirming the role of this sector in the process of attracting investment capital directly abroad. However, alongside that growth, our technical infrastructure has been and is showing limitations in many aspects, such as the degradation of the system: Road traffic, railway, postal fees are quite high... Leading to the role of the public sector. The technical infrastructure sector is degraded, there is a risk of a decrease in capital FDI.

In the past time, in Vietnam, foreign investors have complained a lot about the price of providing technical infrastructure services, which according to investors is too high, especially the telecommunications, aviation and maritime charges. This is considered one of the reasons why Vietnam has not attracted many high-quality FDI projects. Thus, to attract FDI, the technical infrastructure must meet two requirements: synchronization, modernity and a reasonable price. Among the two requirements above, there is one requirement that we have not met, which is the

determination of a fair price. In fact, the requirements for modernity and synchronization are guaranteed or not.

Supporting policies

Currently, enterprises in Vietnam's industrial parks operate in the direction of producing export goods, but are not allowed to sell goods to the domestic market. This is a completely rigid rule. This is not the case for ASEAN countries. Typically, the Philippines allows businesses in industrial zones to exchange goods with the domestic market freely. Vietnam's banking system is still very small and insensitive. This causes a lot of obstacles for foreign investors to get loans.

The issue of assigning land ownership rights to foreigners in Vietnam is completely impossible. Therefore, we need to consider coming up with a suitable land tax price bracket that foreign investors feel satisfy. In addition, relevant procedures must be faster and more transparent, creating confidence for foreign investors.

All countries in the region have removed barriers in administrative procedures, creating a more open environment with simple procedures. However, administrative procedures in Vietnam are still too cumbersome.

Vietnam's investment environment and competitiveness, although improved, still cannot fully meet the requirements of international investors. There are inadequacies in the investment environment such as cumbersome administrative procedures, weak infrastructure and supporting industries, and inflation. FDI from Korea into Vietnam is not sustainable, because it is still too dependent on a few large-scale projects. In recent years, annual FDI capital has relied on a number of billion-dollar projects of investors coming to Vietnam, such as Samsung, LG Display, etc. These are projects with a scale that can bring. However, if these projects are not licensed, or capital is withdrawn, it will greatly affect that locality.

Vietnam is gradually losing its advantage in attracting FDI compared to neighboring countries such as Thailand and Indonesia, due to the gradual loss of advantages in terms of labor, resources and preferential policies. Recently, the rise of India can also be considered as a big challenge for Vietnam in attracting FDI. Vietnam is now having to choose more quality investment projects such as high technology, high added value and less environmental pollution, which means the number of FDI inflows will be reduced. In the context of the industrial revolution 4.0, technology plays an important role in economic development as well as attracting foreign investment. However, limitations in the process of industrialization and modernization are really a big challenge for Vietnam to achieve the expected FDI attraction goals.

5. CONCLUSION

Since 1977, Vietnam's foreign direct investment (FDI) policies have evolved significantly, reflecting the country's broader shift from a centrally planned economy to an open, market-oriented system. The transformation began with the 1977 Investment Charter and was solidified with the Foreign Investment Law of 1987, followed by a series of amendments and reforms that progressively opened Vietnam's economy to global investors. Major milestones—such as the Doi Moi reforms, WTO accession in 2007, and the enactment of unified investment laws in 2005 and 2020—marked crucial turning points in aligning Vietnam's legal framework with international standards. These reforms have resulted in substantial inflows of FDI, contributing to industrial development, export growth, job creation, and GDP expansion. FDI has played a vital role in Vietnam's economic transformation, particularly in manufacturing and processing sectors, while also strengthening integration into regional and global value chains. Despite these achievements, challenges remain.

Legal inconsistencies, complex administrative procedures, underdeveloped infrastructure, and limited high-tech transfer continue to hinder Vietnam's ability to attract higher-quality investments. The government's recent efforts to streamline processes, prioritize high-value sectors, and enhance policy transparency are positive steps forward. To sustain its attractiveness in an increasingly competitive region, Vietnam must continue refining its investment climate, focusing not just on quantity but also on the quality and sustainability of FDI. The country's future success will depend on its ability to adapt its policy framework to global trends, support innovation, and ensure a level playing field for all investors.

References

- 1) Bộ Chính trị (2019). Nghị quyết số 50-NQ/TW ngày 20/8/2019 của Bộ Chính trị về định hướng hoàn thiện thể chế, chính sách, nâng cao chất lượng, hiệu quả hợp tác đầu tư nước ngoài đến năm 2030
- 2) Borensztein, E., De Gregorio, J., & Lee, J. W. (1998). How does foreign direct investment affect economic growth? *Journal of International Economics*
- 3) Christian Delaunay, C. Richard Torrisi (2012). *FDI in Vietnam: An Empirical Study of an Economy in Transition*, Journal of Emerging Knowledge on Emerging Markets
- 4) Cooper, Richard N. (2008), Economic aspects of the Cold War, 1962-1975. *WCFIA Working Paper 2008-2018*.
- 5) Do Nhat Hoang (2014). *Quá trình hình thành và phát triển của Luật đầu tư nước ngoài tại Việt Nam*, Trang thông tin điện tử đầu tư nước ngoài, Bộ kế hoạch và đầu tư, <https://fia.mpi.gov.vn/Detail/CatID/80a3a429-cc68-4621-94a89ebecf86aae6/NewsID/1b85b856-4f4f-4a34-a162-c1851888298b>, Read: 25/9/2021
- 6) GSO (2021). Tổng cục thống kê, *Triển vọng thu hút đầu tư nước ngoài vào Việt Nam năm 2021*, <https://www.gso.gov.vn/du-lieu-va-so-lieu-thong-ke/2021/04/trien-vong-thu-hut-dau-tu-nuoc-ngoai-vao-viet-nam-nam-2021/>, Read: 24/9/2021
- 7) Kim Sunyoung (Sunny) & Kim Minhyung (Michelle) (2021). *Tax planning strategies for South Korean investors*, <https://law.asia/south-korea-tax-planning/>, Retrieved 09/25/2021
- 8) Le Dang Doanh (2002). Foreign Direct Investment in Viet Nam: Results, Achievements, Challenges and Prospect, *International Monetary Fund Conference on Foreign Direct Investment Hanoi*
- 9) Lee Min-hyung (2019). *Korea regains biggest foreign investor status in Vietnam*, https://www.koreatimes.co.kr/www/biz/2019/12/175_280920.html, Retrieved 09/25/2021
- 10) Mark Harrison (2000), Soviet Industrial Production: Real Growth and Hidden Inflation, *Journal of Comparative Economics* 28:1 (2000), pp. 134-55
- 11) Ministry of Planning and Investment (2018). *30 years of FDI mobilization in Vietnam: New vision, new opportunities in new era*, Hanoi
- 12) Nguyen Duc (2021). *Triển vọng thu hút FDI van 'sang'*, <https://baoquocte.vn/trien-vong-thu-hut-fdi-van-sang-158673.html>, Retrieved 09/25/2021
- 13) Phuong Anh (2021). *South Korean investors remain upbeat on Vietnam potentials*, <https://e.vnexpress.net/news/business/economy/south-korean-investors-remain-upbeat-on-vietnam-potentials-4236328.html>, Retrieved 09/25/2021

- 14) Tran Ngoc (2021). *Lieu dong von FDI co roi khoi Viet Nam?* <https://vov.vn/kinh-te/lieu-dong-von-fdi-co-roi-khoi-viet-nam-888858.vov>, Retrieved 09/25/2021
- 15) Tran Thi Anh Dao, Dang Thi Thanh Binh (2013). *FDI and Growth in Vietnam: A Critical Survey*, Journal of Economics and Development Vol. 15, No.3, December 2013, pp. 91 – 116
- 16) Trinh Hoai Nam (2015). “The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth: Evidence from Vietnam”, <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234682627.pdf>
- 17) Vietnam Investment Review (2020). “Learning lessons for Vietnam’s future prosperity”, <https://vir.com.vn/learning-lessons-for-vietnams-future-prosperity-73331.html>
- 18) Vo Thanh Tri, Nguyen Duong Anh (2012). “Experiences of Vietnam in FDI Promotion: Some Lessons for Myanmar”, https://www.ide.go.jp/library/English/Publish/Reports/Brc/pdf/10_04.pdf
- 19) Vo, T T and Nguyen, A D., (2012). “Experiences of Vietnam in FDI Promotion: Some Lessons for Myanmar.” In Economic Reforms in Myanmar: Pathways and Prospects, edited by Hank Lim and Yasuhiro Yamada, *BRC Research Report No.10*, Bangkok Research Center, IDE-JETRO, Bangkok, Thailand.